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“Vocatives as a Means of Expressing Subjective Evaluation in the Process of Speech Communication”

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Annotation: Speech communication is a complex and distinctive sphere through which every individual expresses their identity. In the process of verbal interaction, a person aims either to convey certain information or to receive it. At the same time, behind every piece of information, the speaker’s evaluative attitude is also reflected.

Keywords: Speech communication, vocatives, subjective evaluation, pragmatics, linguistic expression, communicative intention, speech act, emotional-expressive meaning, interpersonal communication, evaluative attitude.

Through speech activity, a person obtains information about objects, events, actions, states, and characteristics that they have not directly witnessed. Human beings accumulate the life experiences gained by their ancestors and pass them on to future generations⁶.

The importance of language in the life, culture, and spirituality of any nation is immeasurable. As a mirror of culture, language reflects not only the real world surrounding human beings, but also such phenomena as a nation’s identity, character, traditions and customs, and its perception of the world. Through language, the material and spiritual values created by a people are preserved in oral and written sources. Language serves as a means of transmitting culture from one generation to another and conveys the heritage of ancestors to future generations. At the same time, it helps people to properly evaluate reality and interpersonal relations.

Feelings arising under various influences, the attitudes that generate them, and the process of evaluation resulting from these attitudes are interconnected phenomena that express philosophical concepts such as sensation, perception, and cognition, all of which reveal the essence of different emotions. In the expression of psychological states, the relationship between emotion and evaluation is one of the central issues. Our feelings toward people, objects, and events determine the way we evaluate them⁷.

“In modern Uzbek, the grammatical and lexical expression of vocatives is highly diverse. Nevertheless, despite this diversity, their expression is described as

⁶ Nurmonov A. Lingvistik tadqiqot metodologiyasi va metodlari. –T., 2010. 5-bet.

⁷ Pardayev Z. Nutq innovatsiyasi va ularda baho munosabatining ifodalanishi.// O”TA,2009. 1-son, 106-bet.

follows: ‘A vocative is expressed by a word in the form of address. Words functioning as vocatives are usually nouns in the nominative case; however, substantivized words may also occur in this function.’, ‘A vocative is usually expressed by a noun in the nominative case or by adjectives and participles functioning as nouns.’⁸, ‘A vocative is usually expressed by a personal noun or by substantivized words.’ these pieces of information only express the grammatical features of vocatives.

As a syntactic unit, the vocative has specific lexical-grammatical features. In addition, since it expresses the person or object to whom the speaker’s speech is directed, it is considered a powerful stylistic device. Vocatives reflect the speaker’s attitude toward the listener and carry an evaluative nuance (positive, negative, neutral, or emphatic).

In literary discourse, vocatives express either negative or positive evaluative relations. Vocatives expressing negative evaluation serve as a strong stylistic device in literary works, helping to depict characters, reveal psychological states, and individualize a character’s speech. For example: 1. “Hey!” he said, stretching his neck like a rooster. “Don’t get carried away just because you’re the chairman! Is this the first time you’re seeing Husan Duma, you fool!” (O’.H.). 2. “That’s exactly it, my lady! She didn’t run away with anyone.” (O’.H.)

The process of analyzing literary speech shows that vocatives express the following negative pragmatic meanings:

1. Meaning of anger and irritation:

“Hey, not a guest but a fool!” the elder said angrily, waving his hand. “Get lost!” (O’.H.). “Why are you twisting the words, comrade chairman? Just say there is no truth—leave it at that!” (O’.H.)

In the first situation, the meaning of irritation arises because a negatively evaluative word (“fool”) is used as a vocative. In the second case, the negative meaning of the vocative (“comrade chairman”) can only be understood from the context.

2. Meaning of sarcasm and irony:

1. “At least try to offer some tea, comrade tractor driver!” (O’.H.). “So you live in the same place as Yo’ldoshxon Usmonov, comrade Khajayip!” I said without putting down the receiver. (O’.H.)

In both cases, irony is expressed through the use of the word “comrade” before the vocative.

3. Meaning of dissatisfaction:

1. “You scared the life out of me, shorty!” he said, relieved. (O’.H.).
2. “Aren’t you ashamed to call your own brother like that, you donkey!” (O’.H.)

4. Meaning of threat and intimidation:

1. “Move your cart, you fool, don’t interfere in others’ affairs.” (O’.H.)

⁸ O’zbek tili grammatikasi. II to’m. Sintaksis. –Fan, 1976. 57-bet.

2. “Go on, you cursed one!” the elder angrily kicked one of the oxen in the stomach. (O’.H.)

5. Meaning of mockery:

“Do you want to die five days before your time, you idiot!” Abduvali muttered and followed me anyway. (O’.H.)

In some cases, words that semantically express a positive attitude are also used to convey a negative meaning. The negative connotative meaning intended through vocatives can easily be identified through contextual analysis. For example:

1. “Did your heart ache for Marza’s sister, madam!” he said ironically.

2. “What do you say, young man?!” he said, turning sharply to Muzaffar. (O’.H.)

Vocatives in speech and within literary texts can also express various positive attitudes. For example:

1. “Oh, why didn’t you say so, uncle,” she said and took off the skullcap from her head. (O’.H.)

2. “Did you hear that, Duma! Our soldiers who went on the offensive have joined the partisans.” (O’.H.)

3. “You, Husan aka, are a true farmer.” (O’.H.)

In the first example, the vocative is expressed by a kinship term (“uncle”), which conveys a sense of joy. In the second example, a nickname (“Duma”) is used as a vocative and also expresses happiness. In the third example, a name form (“Husan aka”) is used to convey respect.

Vocatives expressing positive evaluation are used to convey the following pragmatic meanings to the reader:

1. Meaning of goodwill:

2. “You’ve come, brother, let’s rest a little!” (O’.H.)

3. “Come on, sisters! Don’t give up!” (O’.H.)

4. Meaning of affection:

5. “You’ve scored seventeen already, hero!” (O’.H.)

6. “Come on, in-laws!” (O’.H.)

7. Meaning of plea:

8. “At least do not be offended by your mother for the sake of this innocent child, my dear son!” (O’.H.)

9. “Get up, soldier!” (O’.H.)

10. Meaning of reverence:

11. “Let’s go, bring the light, mother!” (O’.H.)

12. “We don’t have time, dear aunt!” (O’.H.)

13. Meaning of respect:

14. “Honorable comrade Abdurahmonov!” (O’.H.)

15. “Oh, time has run out, teacher!” (O’.H.)

16. Meaning of encouragement:

17. “Well done, brave ones!” (O’.H.)

18. “Be happy, dear sister! Be grateful that your son is alive.” (O’.H.)

19. Meaning of consolation:

20. "Please, dear father!" (O'.H.)

21. "Enough, my friend!" (O'.H.)

22. Meaning of joking:

23. "Come on, comrade!" (O'.H.)

24. "You really turned out well, my friend!" (O'.H.)

25. Meaning of pleading:

26. "Take me too, brother! Just once." (O'.H.)

27. "Come on, bring the light, mother!" (O'.H.)

Usually, vocatives used to attract the listener's attention or to address them—especially complex forms or those containing interjections—occur at the beginning of a sentence. In such cases, the speaker's evaluative attitude toward the situation is clearly expressed. For example:

1. "Munavvar, forgive me, Munavvar, I will die without you!" (O'.H.)

2. "People, don't think briefly. A war will break out soon." (O'.H.)

Vocatives occurring at the end of a sentence express the speaker's modal attitude. For example:

1. "You've broken your arm, brave young man!" (O'.H.)

2. "At least do not be offended by your mother for the sake of this innocent child, my dear son!" (O'.H.)

3. "Speak to your brother with respect, okay, my daughter?" (O'.H.)

4. "There will be a day when we will see you too, Muzaffarxon!" (O'.H.)

5. "Do you have any conscience, sister!" (O'.H.)

As can be seen, placing vocatives at the end of sentences expresses various additional meanings: affection, plea, request, joy, and dissatisfaction.

It is clear that vocatives in speech communication are not only used to attract the listener's attention, but also play an important role in expressing the speaker's emotions. Vocatives have a significant role in conveying the speaker's psychological state, inner feelings, and attitude toward a situation.

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